

EPR Spectra of Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes of some Tetradentate Schiff Bases

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Epr spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of some tetradentate Schiff bases have been described. Various epr parameters and bonding coefficients have been calculated and discussed.

Vanadium is widely distributed¹ in rocks, soils, plants, animals and to a lesser extent in waters and has been shown to be present in the marine animal, *Phallusia mamillata* (sea squirt)² and land plants, *Amanita muscaria* (mushroom)³. *Amanita muscaria*, fly agaric, is an anomaly among plants in that it concentrates vanadium. The natural product amavadin, has been isolated and characterised⁴. Most importantly oxovanadium(IV) is concentrated in the solid asphaltic fraction of petroleum⁵ combined with porphyrin⁶ as well as non-porphyrin ligands. More and more data on the spectral properties of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes are needed to establish correlation between the spectral parameters and the ligand type. There have been sincere efforts for identifying ligands for oxovanadium(IV) present in the biological^{7,8} and geological^{9,10} systems.

In this paper we describe synthesis and epr spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of tetradentate Schiff bases shown in Fig. 1 and listed in Table 1. Aromatic amines are weaker bases as compared to the aliphatic amines. In aliphatic

of electrons on nitrogen is involved in the interaction with π -electron system of benzene ring. This difference is also expected to show up in the donor properties of the corresponding Schiff bases.

TABLE 1—SCHIFF BASES USED

Sl. no.*	R	R'	Ketone/Aldehyde	Ligand Abbreviations
<i>Type-I^a</i>				
1.	CH ₃	CH ₃	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone	(H ₃ hma-phn)
2.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-propiofenone	(H ₃ hmp-phn)
3.	C ₆ H ₇	CH ₃	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-butyrophenone	(H ₃ hmb-phn)
4.	H	H	Salicylaldehyde	(H ₃ sal-phn)
<i>Type-II^b</i>				
5.	CH ₃	CH ₃	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone	(H ₃ hma-en)
6.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-propiofenone	(H ₃ hmp-en)
7.	C ₆ H ₇	CH ₃	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-butyrophenone	(H ₃ hmb-en)
8.	H	H	Salicylaldehyde	(H ₃ sal-en)

*Diamine used : ^ao-Phenylenediamine, ^bethylenediamine.

Fig. 1. Structure of the ligands and complexes.

amines, the availability of lone-pair of electrons is increased due to +I effect of alkyl group. In aromatic amines, on the other hand, the lone-pair

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 2) are soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide and partially soluble in ethanol.

Infrared spectra : Important ir bands and their assignments are given in Table 3. Data on a large number and variety of oxovanadium(IV) complexes suggest¹¹ this band to lie in the range 985 ± 50 cm^{-1} . Position of the $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ for the present complexes lie in the range $960-980$ cm^{-1} . The $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ for the complexes of ethylene diamine based Schiff bases have lower values as compared to the complexes of phenylenediamine Schiff bases. Low $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ frequency, signifies a $\text{V=O} \cdots \text{V=O}$ interaction in solid state. Another ir band of structural importance in the compound under discussion is $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. In VO(sal-phn) this band appears at 1600 cm^{-1} , 18 cm^{-1}

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA

Sl. no	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)	
			V	N
1.	VO(hma-phn)	Brown	11.35 (11.46)	6.30 (6.40)
2.	VO(hmp-phn)	Brown	10.65 (10.75)	5.95 (6.02)
3.	VO(hmb-phn)	Brown	10.05 (10.14)	5.60 (5.68)
4.	VO(sal-phn)	Green	13.00 (13.12)	7.30 (7.35)
5.	VO(hma-en)	Black	15.75 (15.87)	8.80 (8.89)
6.	VO(hmp-en)	Gray	14.50 (14.58)	8.10 (8.16)
7.	VO(hmb-en)	Green	13.40 (13.48)	7.45 (7.54)
8.	VO(sal-en)	Green	16.00 (16.13)	8.95 (9.03)

TABLE 3—RELEVANT IR BANDS (cm⁻¹)*

Compd.	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{C=C}$	ν_{C-N}	ν_{C-O}	$\nu_{V=O}$	ν_{V-N}
VO(hma-phn)	1 640m 1 618m	1 600m	1 360m	1 320m	978w	520w
VO(hmp-phn)	1 650s	1 605sh	1 360m	1 338m	980s	540b
VO(hmb-phn)	—	1 610m	1 380	—	980s	530b
VO(sal-phn)	1 600vs 1 580m	1 525vs	1 370s	1 318vs	980vs	540vs
VO(hma-en)	—	1 620w	1 370w	1 280w	970s	585b
VO(hmp-en)	—	1 620w	—	—	960s	560b
VO(hmb-en)	—	1 590w	—	—	960s	530s
VO(sal-en)	1 618vs 1 590sh	1 530s	1 330s	1 300vs	980vs	—

*vs≡very strong, s≡strong, m≡medium, w≡weak, sh≡shoulder, b≡broad.

lower than that in VO(sal-en) and other alkyl bridged series¹². Reduction in $\nu_{C=N}$ suggests distortion from the planar geometry around V=O. Such distortion is known for the Cu^{II} analogues¹⁴. Kolawole *et al.*¹⁵ reported some oxovanadium(IV) complexes derived from substituted 2-hydroxyaromatic aldehyde and aromatic diamines. Also, the

$\nu_{C=N}$ band for both VO(sal-en) and VO(sal-phn) are split as doublet. This splitting suggests in these two cases that the two azomethine groups are distorted¹³ below and above the horizontal plane more than in other cases. Such distortion of the C=N groups implies that the overlap of π -orbitals is out of alignment and that conjugation may not be so effective.

Electronic spectra : Electronic spectra of the complexes are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The observed absorption bands and their assignments are given in Table 4. The assignments have been made following Ballhausen and Gray¹⁶. Both in dimethylformamide and nujol, the band II for the complexes of the salicylaldehyde Schiff bases are shifted towards lower energies as compared to those in the spectra of the complexes of ketone Schiff bases. VO(sal-phn) and VO(sal-en) show nearly similar spectra both in nujol and dimethylformamide. For the same ketone, the phenylene diamine Schiff base complexes show bands at higher energy compared to the ethylenediamine Schiff base complexes. For the same diamine, the complexes of ketone Schiff bases show band II at higher energy than do the complexes of aldehyde Schiff bases.

Epr spectra : Representative epr spectra of the complexes are given in Figs. 4 and 5.

Epr spectra in solution : For dimethylformamide solutions at room temperature, all complexes show eight-line isotropic epr spectra. The eight lines are due to the coupling of the unpaired electron with the large moment of the nearly 100% abundant ⁵¹V nucleus ($I=7/2$). The g -values and vanadium nuclear hyperfine splitting constants are tabulated in Table 5. Ligand nitrogen or hydrogen super-hyperfine splittings are not observed. This indicates that the unpaired electron is in the b_{2g} (d_{xy}) orbital localised on the metal, thus excluding any possibility of its direct interaction with the ligand¹⁷. Frozen solution spectra are anisotropic and two sets of resonance components, one each due to the

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹)

Transition	In nujol mull				In DMF			
	VO(hma-phn)	VO(hmp-phn)	VO(hmb-phn)	VO(sal-phn)	VO(hma-phn)	VO(hmp-phn)	VO(hmb-phn)	VO(sal-phn)
² B _g — ² E (Band I)	—	—	—	—	12 500	—	12 200	13 160
² B _g — ² B _g (Band II)	—	—	19 800	16 950	—	—	—	17 000
² B _g — ² A _g (Band III)	—	—	—	21 275	—	—	—	—
	VO(hma-en)	VO(hmp-en)	VO(hmb-en)	VO(sal-en)	VO(hma-en)	VO(hmp-en)	VO(hmb-en)	VO(sal-en)
² B _g — ² E (Band I)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
² B _g — ² B _g (Band II)	—	16 000	—	16 950	17 515	16 130	19 610	16 920
² B _g — ² A _g (Band III)	23 810	—	21 275	—	—	—	—	21 505

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra (in nujol) of complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

parallel and the perpendicular features, are observed (Fig. 5).

The spectra of VO(hma-phn), VO(hma-en) and VO(hmb-en) show splitting on g_{\parallel} signals (Fig. 6). Such splittings are indicative of the presence of more than one species. This situation has earlier¹⁹ been explained in terms of one of the following reasons: (i) isomers with different structure, (ii) monomer-dimer equilibria or (iii) species containing molecules of solvent coordinated and noncoordinated. In the present case the apparent reason is different degrees of associations of the solvent molecule at the time of glass formation.

A-values vs g-values :

Boucher *et al.*⁹ studied epr and spectral properties of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of a variety of

Fig. 3. Electronic spectra (in DMF) of complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

ligands. They showed an empirical linear relationship between A_{\parallel} and $(g_{\perp} - g_{\parallel})$ and A_{\perp} and $(g_{\perp} - g_{\parallel})$. The plots are shown in Fig. 7. The data points for the complexes under study lie quite close to these straight lines. It may be noted that the data points for VO(hma-en), VO(hmp-en), VO(hma-phn), VO(hmp-phn) and VO(hmb-phn) cluster at one point at higher A_{\parallel} values and those for VO(sal-en), VO(sal-phn) and VO(hmb-en) cluster at another point at lower A_{\parallel} values.

Anisotropy in the g-values, i.e. $g_{\perp} - g_{\parallel}$, gives a measure of the in-plane ligand field strength. Smaller value of $g_{\perp} - g_{\parallel}$ means larger in-plane ligand field strength (Table 6). The trend in g_{\parallel} values also yields the same result.

The A_{\parallel} for the complexes of ketone Schiff bases are all similar and greater than the values for the complexes of the aldehyde Schiff bases. VO(hmb-en)

Fig 4. Epr spectrum of VO(hmp-en) in DMF at room temperature.

Fig. 5. Epr spectrum of VO(hmp-en) in DMF at liquid nitrogen temperature.

TABLE 5—EPR PARAMETERS AND BONDING COEFFICIENTS

Parameter	VO(hma-phn)	VO(hmp-phn)	VO(hmb-phn)	VO(sal-phn)	VO(hma-en)	VO(hmp-en)	VO(hmb-en)	VO(sal-en)
$\nu_{V=O}$	978	980	980	980	970	980	980	980
g_{\parallel}	1.933	1.937	1.935	1.957	1.936	1.937	1.956	1.955
g_{\perp}	1.987	1.985	1.989	1.988	1.986	1.987	1.989	1.987
g_0	1.971	1.969	1.971	1.978	1.969	1.970	1.978	1.976
A_{\parallel}	191.14	195.71	196	173	196	196.42	172	171.14
A_{\perp}	71	70	69	57	67	68.71	56.5	58
A_0	111	111.57	111.42	95.71	110	111.28	95	95
K	0.784	0.787	0.784	0.679	0.775	0.769	0.673	0.677
$(\beta_{\parallel}^*)^2$	0.963	1.039	1.016	0.947	1.035	1.025	0.941	0.921
$(\beta_{\perp}^*)^2$	—	—	—	0.604	0.826	0.761	0.716	0.645
$(\epsilon_{\pi}^*)^2$	0.602	—	0.486	0.603	—	—	—	—

Fig. 6. Epr spectrum of VO(hmb-en) in DMF at liquid nitrogen temperature

is a peculiar exception, which has value equal to those for VO(sal-en) and VO(sal-phn). Dickson *et al.*¹⁰ showed a correlation between A_0 and g_0 for vanadyl complexes (Fig. 8) having a variety of equatorial donor atoms of the type VO(S_4), VO(N_4), VO(N_2O_2) and VO(O_4). The parameters cluster in domains according to the ligand environment (Fig. 8) correlations such as this have been used to speciate VO²⁺ compounds in petroleum^{9,10} and to help identify coordinating functional groups in proteins⁷ and in subcellular fractions of rat liver⁶.

Holyk²⁰ observed a similar correlation between A_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} (Fig. 9). This correlation is perhaps more useful in that g_{\perp} depends directly on the in-plane ligand field. In the present compounds all the data points lie outside the zones defined for VO(N_2O_2) in the A_{\perp} vs g_{\parallel} plots (as also in A_0 vs g_0 plot). The reason for this deviation appears to be the different solvent systems used. Entire data of Holyk¹⁹ were obtained from aqueous solutions. The present compounds are not soluble in water and hence the data have been collected from DMF

Fig. 7. Plots of epr parameters for oxovanadium(IV) complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

TABLE 6 - $g_{\perp} - g_{||}$ AND g_0 VALUES

Compd.	$g_{\perp} - g_{ }$	g_0
VO(hma-phn)	0.048	1.971
VO(hmp-phn)	0.048	1.969
VO(hmb-phn)	0.054	1.971
VO(sal-phn)	0.021	1.978
VO(hma-en)	0.049	1.969
VO(hmp-en)	0.050	1.970
VO(hmb-en)	0.033	1.978
VO(-sal-en)	0.032	1.976

Fig. 8. Plots of g_0 vs A_0 of complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

solutions. While comparing epr parameters of different complexes, special attention should be paid to the solvent used, solvent coordination in the axial position and hydrogen bonding to the vanadyl oxygen can have a very pronounced effect on the spectral parameters^{9,18,21}. Most interesting is the behaviour of VO(hmb-en) which cluster with VO(sal-phn) and VO(sal-en), rather than with the complexes of the ketone Schiff bases.

Fig. 9. Plots of $A_{||}$ vs $g_{||}$ of complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

g Values and electronic transitions energies : The g -factors are related to the optical transition energies through the equations,

$$g_{\perp} = 2.002 - \frac{8(\beta_2^*)^2 (\beta_1^*)^2 \epsilon}{\Delta E_{x^2-y^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$g_{\perp} = 2.002 - \frac{2(\beta_2^*)^2 (\epsilon_{\pi}^*)^2 \epsilon}{\Delta E_{xz, yz}} \quad (2)$$

where $(\beta_2^*)^2$, $(\beta_1^*)^2$ and $(\epsilon_{\pi}^*)^2$ are the unpaired electron metal orbital populations in the $|xy\rangle$, $|x^2-y^2\rangle$ and $|xz, yz\rangle$ orbitals respectively²². ϵ is the one electron spin-orbit coupling constant of vanadium. Holyk²⁰ showed a straight line relationship between $1/\Delta E_{x^2-y^2}$ and g_{\perp} . In the case of complexes of ketone Schiff bases, i.e. VO(hma-en), VO(hmp-en) and VO(hmb-en), the data points are closer to the linear regression line (Fig. 10), compared to the complexes of aldehyde Schiff bases.

Fig. 10. Plot of $1/\Delta E_{x^2-y^2}$ vs $g_{||}$ of complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

Holyk²⁰ also showed a straight line relationship between $1/\Delta E_{xz, yz}$ and g_{\perp} . Our data points lie away from the linear regression lines (Fig. 11). As suggested in the previous paragraph, the deviations are due to difference in the solvent system. Also the deviations indicate variation in the bonding coefficients, $(\beta_2^*)^2$, $(\beta_1^*)^2$ and $(\epsilon_{\pi}^*)^2$.

Fig. 11. Plot of $1/\Delta E_{xz}$ vs g_1 of complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

Bonding coefficients and isotropic contact term: $(\beta_1^*)^2$ is the bonding coefficient for $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The value of in-plane σ -bonding coefficient $(\beta_1^*)^2$ generally follows the σ -donor strength of the ligand, i.e. $(\beta_1^*)^2$ decreases as the covalent bonding increases. The $(\beta_1^*)^2$ values (Table 7) of the complexes of aldehyde Schiff bases are lower than the complexes of ketone Schiff bases. From the criterion given above, the aldehyde Schiff bases appear to be stronger ligand. Also the $(\beta_1^*)^2$ value for VO(sal-phn) is lower

TABLE 7—VALUES OF BONDING COEFFICIENTS AND ISOTROPIC CONTACT TERM

Compd.	$(\beta_1^*)^2$	$(\beta_1^*)^2$	K
VO(hma-phn)	0.963	—	0.784
VO(hmp-phn)	1.039	—	0.787
VO(hmb-phn)	1.016	—	0.784
VO(sal-phn)	0.947	0.604	0.679
VO(hma-en)	0.914	0.785	0.774
VO(hmp-en)	1.025	0.761	0.769
VO(hmb-en)	0.941	0.716	0.673
VO(sal-en)	0.921	0.645	0.677

than that for VO(sal-en), revealing their relative ligand field strength. $(\beta_1^*)^2$ values decrease in the following order: VO(hma-en) > VO(hmp-en) > VO(hmb-en) > VO(sal-en) > VO(sal-phn).

Fig. 12a shows plot of K vs $(\beta_1^*)^2$. A linear relationship between K and $(\beta_1^*)^2$ has earlier been demonstrated by Boucher *et al.*⁹. Data point for the present complexes also obey this linearity (Fig. 12a). K , the isotropic contact term, is related to the amount of unpaired electron density at the vanadium nucleus since the orbital containing the unpaired electron, d_{xy} , has zero electron density at the nucleus and does not mix with the metal $4s$ -orbital, the only way of putting the unpaired

Fig. 12. Plots of (a) K vs $(\beta_1^*)^2$ and (b) K vs $1/\Delta E_{x^2-y^2}$ of complexes (compound numbers are given as in Table 2).

electron density at the nucleus is the spin polarisation mechanism²³. The unpaired electron in d_{xy} orbital formally creates unpaired electron density in the filled $2s$ and $3s$ orbitals, which have electron density at the nucleus.

Isotropic contact term (K) is also related to the energy of the ${}^2B_2(xy) \rightarrow {}^2B_1(x^2-y^2)$ by the relationship $\Delta E_{x^2-y^2}$ (kK) = 13.0/ K . A plot of $1/\Delta E_{x^2-y^2}$ vs K for a variety of ligand is, therefore, linear. The data points for the present complexes lie quite close to this line (Fig. 12b).

The bonding coefficient for d_{xz} and d_{yz} orbitals, $(\epsilon_{\pi'})^2$, measures the covalency of the V=O bond. It also indirectly shows the strength of the in-plane ligands. The value of this parameter for VO(hmb-phn) is smaller than that for VO(hma-phn), suggests stronger covalent character of V=O and weaker in-plane ligand field in the former (Table 5).

Experimental

Preparation of ligands : 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl ketones were prepared by the method described earlier²⁴. For preparing the Schiff bases, ethanolic solutions of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl ketones and *o*-phenylenediamine/ethylenediamine were mixed in 2 : 1 ratio. The contents were shaken vigorously and refluxed for ~10 min when maroon to yellow coloured Schiff bases separated out. These were filtered, washed with 1 : 1 ethanol and dried in an oven at 60°, H₂sal-phn and H₂sal-en Schiff bases were also prepared in the same way by coupling of the diamines with salicylaldehyde.

Preparation of complexes : Ethanolic solution of the respective ligand and aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate were mixed together keeping the metal-ligand ratio as 1 : 1. The complex separated out instantaneously, was filtered, washed with water and 50% ethanol and dried over P₂O₅ in a vacuum desiccator.

Infrared spectra (KBr) of the complexes were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (nujol/DMF) on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer and epr spectra (DMF) on a Varian E-112 spectrometer at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature using TCNE as field marker.

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